

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SYSTEM OF PSYCHOLOGICAL EDUCATIONAL WORK WITH SCHOOLCHILDREN FROM INCOMPLETE FAMILIES

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Abstract

The object of the activity of every social educator and worker is the child's personality. The child opens his eyes to the world in the family, from the first day he assimilates the norms of coexistence, takes from his family the good and the bad, in general, everything that is characteristic of that family, when he grows up, he repeats in his own family what he saw in the parental family, grows up, becomes socialized. In the family, the child's relationship with the surrounding world is regulated. He gains experience in spirituality, cultural norms of behavior. The family is the core, the foundation of society. In the life of every person, his family plays a special role. The issue of the family is such a big issue that it has been the object of research of various researchers for many years. When we look at the scientific and pedagogical literature, we can find different opinions on this issue. S. Guliyev notes that the state of the state depends on the state of the family. In the family, there is definitely a moral connection between parents and children. At the same time, there are connections between each family that forms the core of the state and various other families.

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The morality of each family, the morality of the state, the social status of each family is an indicator of the social status of the state, and the economic status of each family is an indicator of the economic status of the state. In addition to fulfilling social duties, the family cultivates a personality corresponding to its cultural, moral and social level. Socialization in the family depends on the composition of the family. Today, it can be said that there are no longer large families, such as those in previous times, that is, families with grandparents, aunts, uncles, etc. The formation of personality within the family changes depending on the relationship between family members.

In family relationships, family members usually have different expectations from each other. Thus, a woman wants to see her husband as a sincere, respectful, caring, courageous, intelligent person. Men, in turn, want to see their spouses as sincere, kind, caring, gentle, beautiful. Of course, the parties always bring these expectations to each other's attention before getting married. However, sometimes after getting married, some dissatisfaction arises. In this case, the man, the woman, or both parties may be dissatisfied. The reason for this may be that the parties encounter a completely different family model from the family model they have built in their minds. When this happens, divorce occurs.

There are various types of families. One of them is incomplete families.

An incomplete family is a single-parent family, the number of which has been increasing in recent years. In these families, the parent is usually the mother, and rarely the father. American researchers have found that in 2.8% of families, the father raises the child alone. Such families arise as a result of divorce, the death of one of the parents, or when a child is born out of wedlock. If the spouses do not live together, but in separate places, this is also considered an incomplete family. Such families need state care [5, P.114].

An unsuccessful family is essentially a sociological and socio-psychological phenomenon, its characteristics are mainly studied within the framework of these sciences. An unsuccessful family has many socio-psychological problems. An incomplete family is a purely demographic phenomenon. Each of the above-mentioned incomplete families has its own characteristics. However, what they have in common is that in each case the child grows up with only one parent.

In incomplete families resulting from death, each of the family members is deeply shaken to the same extent. Children from such families differ from children from other incomplete families in that they already know that they will never be able to see and communicate with the parent they have lost. This creates a feeling of lack in them. And the child lives with that feeling of lack throughout his life. This feeling always has its psychological impact on that person. Such people are always distinguished from their peers by their sensitivity.

Divorce and its consequences. Divorce, which is a global demographic process, is one of the greatest scourges of the 21st century. This process is characteristic of all developed countries. Since the 80s of the last century, this issue has become a problem that worries the world. Since then, various methods have been used to find a solution to such a big problem as divorce. Despite all the measures taken, the number of divorces continues to increase day by day. It should also be noted that the number and reasons for divorce are not the same in every country and city.

"A comparative analysis of demographic literature shows that divorce mainly occurs during the adolescence of children. Adolescence is one of the most complex periods in the formation of a student's personality. The formation of feelings and inclinations for adulthood is the main feature of that period. The formation of self-awareness and moral awareness in this age of

friendship and love attracts attention as a major event in the development of a student's personality" [5, p.255]

According to J. Kelly and J. Wallerstein, the bitter consequences of divorce have a completely negative impact on the personality of the child being formed, his spiritual and cultural world, his communication with friends, relatives, people, and his relationship with his mother and father. It causes the formation of negative qualities such as distrust, fear, and insecurity in children. For this reason, the consequences of the divorce process that occurs during a child's adolescence are more severe. In such cases, sharp differences between children's behavior at school and at home are evident. Not only do children's academic performance deteriorate, but their relationships and communication with people around them also deteriorate.

The period before divorce is also a very difficult period for a child. This period is characterized by psychologically and pedagogically difficult and complicated situations for both parents and children. Factors such as arguments, disagreements, quarrels, inappropriate behavior, insults, psychological trauma, violence, etc. between father and mother naturally have a huge impact on the child's psychology.

In families resulting from divorce, the conflict between mother and father almost never ends. Children often stay with their mother. In this case, mothers usually create obstacles for their children to meet their

fathers. The mother may have some reason for this. However, this can have certain negative effects on the child's growth, development and psychology. The inability to communicate normally with one of the parents, to use their help, to gain their sympathy and approval affects the child's psyche. The situation becomes even more complicated when the parents begin to make the child feel the hostile attitude between them. That is, the mother criticizes her ex-spouse in front of the child, accuses the child of being against him or, conversely, attributes all this to the father. At this time, the child is left between his two parents and is shaken.

Another feature of an incomplete family is the restructuring of external social relations. A single mother loses a number of acquaintances, because they were from her husband's side. At the same time, lack of time also makes it necessary to reduce external relations. This naturally worsens the child's social relations. This restriction in external relations is accompanied by difficulties in the emotional state of the mother in an incomplete family. Unstable work mood, increased irritability due to the spread of negative emotions due to excessive working hours - all this makes up the psychological microclimate of a single-parent family. Similar experiences, of course, also arise in a single-parent family. However, firstly, single-parent families are less common, and secondly, such families are often supported more intensively with the help of grandparents.